

WOMEN CULTURE AND POLITICS

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Keywords: Women Representation, Cultural Norms, Gender Inequality, Political Participation, Socialization and Beliefs	Abstract: <i>Culture, our way of life, norms, values, religion, laws transferred from generation to generation through socialization has charted the course of women. Beliefs have debarred women from fulfilling their life ambitions, despite their academic prowess, charisma, finance, influence and political fame. No woman has become an elected governor not to talk of the exalted position of a President. Women representation in the National Assembly is dwindling due to our inculcated norms and factors enhanced to debilitate it. Ranging from the mean and degrading words used for women in politics, to the high cost of forms, to the internal party ranglings etc. The struggle continues. The end will justify the course. A broken jinx. (Debilitate, broken jinx, inculcate, prowess, charisma, socialization ranglings, norms).</i>
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INTRODUCTION

Culture is the way of life of a people. Their customs and traditions which include the elements of culture, language, crafts religious festivals outfits etc. culture is a strong determinant in the life of an individual. It's also one of the sources of the constitution of the State.

The norms of a people determine the growth of their aspirations. "Culture is the 'complex whole' of a society including knowledge, beliefs, arts, morals, law customs and habits providing the framework for how people live, relate and survive".

To a great extent culture is disseminated from generation to generation through socialization

as the family, school, peer groups media etc. are agents of socialization. As both material and non-material culture are passed from age to age. Oakley argues that "gender roles are socially constructed and not biologically determined". .." that they can vary greatly across cultures and time period....."

Women the "adult female human" have always faced gender inequality violence, under representation in leadership as Nigerian women are still asking for 30% representation in the Senate despite their signifying excellence, education, charisma, eloquence and so on. Between 2019 and 2023 the 9th Assembly, there were about 13 women.

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“... with total count varying but generally around a dozen through less than 10% of the total members highlighting under representation”.

“... However, it is interesting to note the dwindling number of women elected into the Nation’s parliament has continued in the 10th Assembly. Experts say the situation is deplorable, especially considering the increased agitation for having a gender balanced parliament in the Senate out of 109 senators; three are female which was a reduction from the seven in the 9th Assembly. All female senators in the 9th Assembly lost their re-election bid giving away with rich legislative experience”.

In the House of Representative, sixteen women were sworn in, out of 360 lawmakers an increase compared to 13 in the previous house. The idea that ‘a woman’s place is in the kitchen’ has affected today’s woman negatively as there is a struggle to be seen in the social economic and political landscape of the nation.

“The phrase is still used to enforce traditional roles and limit women’s participation in the public sphere even in the face of gender equality movements”.

Sylvia Walby said *"patriarchy should not be seen as just individual men dominating individual women but as a set of interlocking structures embedded in the society" so she defines patriarchy thus: "A system of social structures and practices in which men dominate, oppress and exploit women"*

Culture was one of the determining factors of Aishatu Dahiru (Binani) the APC Gubernatorial

candidate in the 2023 elections. Mohammad Alabira Nabordo puts it thus.

“... Binani is not facing an incumbent, she is also running against religious and cultural biases that have long stood against women in contest for power in the more conservative part of Nigeria”.

Boboye Abba quipped about Binani.

“Attendance at her campaign rallies was more than that of her rivals the incumbent governor cannot pull her kind of crowd. Because Fintri does not give out welfare despite being the serving governor”.

Considering the religious aspect, the debate was intense as some Islamic clerics preached against her being on ruler of the state.

“... On Friday the day before the election sponsored Islamic clerics hill in their preaching at Jumnat Services, discourage giving the leadership of the state to a woman...”.

This is evident in the Intersectionality theory of Kimberle Crenshaw as it emphasizes that life is a product of *"a matrix of social categories that interact in ways that cannot be separated as challenges and problems of life varies based on the intersection of race and gender"*.

This theory is *"a framework used to understand how various forms of inequality, discrimination and social identities such as race, gender, class, sexuality and disability intersect and overlap....."*.

Invariably people are affected in their courses of life by different factors that shape their destinies, either as privileges or oppression. So our victories or losses are products of our laws, circumstances, customs etc.

Women in Politics seen as “WAYWARD” – Culture

Women in politics are seen as ‘wayward’ prostitutes culturally because women have been over the years meant to be in the kitchen, at home, at the backstage not to be seen or heard in recent times even when more read and adequate in comparison with their contemporaries, are meant to be under the men so a push away from the norm tags are “Wayward”.

“This perception stems from deeply ingrained cultural and religious expectations that defines a woman’s primary role as being within the home as a wife and mother”.

Men Strategize in diverse ways to edge women out of the way. When Natasha Akpoti Uduagha vied for the Gubernatorial seat of Kogi state under the SDP (Political Party) in 2019, it was a ‘battle of the titans’. Men fought to eliminate or frustrate her from the race. Business Day recorded at thus;

“When she ran for governor of Nigeria’s state in 2019, gunmen shot at Natasha Akpoti Uduagha’s cars, her party’s offices were burnt down and her followers were beaten and killed. People called her a prostitute”.

Women must be resolute to be in politics. Determined to stand the wiles of the enemy and pursue their life’s ambition.

Mrs. Duchi Manuga, Labour Party woman leader said this;

“Some of our women also face cyber stalking and intimidation from those who should know better in the cyber space. There are certain people who still regard women in politics as prostitutes ...”Some perceived female

politicians are loose and promiscuous women. But it is not true. There are times we are even attacked directly in political arena during heated debates and they end it with “Who are you?” You people are just prostitutes”.

This is intended to not only humiliate the women in politics but to also intimidate and debar them from aspiring for good position quitting the political arena entirely. However, this stigmatization does not come from men atimes from women too. **Amazing.**

Walby sees through sexuality thus: *“Sexual double standard exists, women are judged negatively for behavior men are praised for....”. “... Media and culture often police female sexuality while celebrating male sexual freedom ” What a world of male dominance.*

Hajia Suleiman quipped

“... the more important obstacle to women participation is the stigmatization of women in politics. Mostly men and even fellow women look down on politically active women as either prostitutes or women who couldn’t keep their marriages”.

INTIMIDATIONS

“Women are outsiders in system which appears to them to come from another planet”

There are different degrees of intimidation from sexual harassment to increase in purchase of nomination forms to internal party reviling before and after party elections.

Senator Natasha Akpoti Uduagari was suspended for six months on March 6th 2025 because of her outcry of her marginalization in the Senate.

“For seven months have not been able to raise my motions. Contribute to debates or take second reading of my bills”.

This is as a result of her rejection of the advances by the Senate President Godswill Akpabio. Life is full of battles, However God never fails as recorded in the book of John Chapter 16 verse 33.

“In the world you have tribulation and trials and distress and frustration but be of good cheer (take courage, be confident, certain, undaunted) for I have overcome the world. I have deprived it of power to harm you and have conquered it for you”.

However, when she formally accused him of sexual harassment Senator Akpabio suspended her for six months. This drama unfolded in its shape and colours and it was obvious Akpabio was not only guilty but has been known for intimidating women both in Politics and other spheres of life. How he intimidated Senator Ireti Kingibe was brought to bear.

“Senate President Godswill Akpabio reportedly intimidated or stopped Senator Ireti Kingibe from being heard during a December 2024 Senate session leading to her temporarily walking out of the chambers”.

This incident generated criticism on the Senate President’s attitude towards female politicians.

Nyeson Wike the Minister for the Federal Capital Territory battle of words with Ireti Kingibe, the Senator representing (FCT) The Federal Capital Territory led to derogatory statements by his aide Iere Okiyinka

“As for the FCT Minister Nyeson Wike, he will not be distracted by someone like Senator Ireti Kingibe who has no other credible identity to

present herself with, except the name of someone she is no longer married to” Olayinka also described her as “Shameless and alleged that several of her Legislative aides had quit due to none payment of salaries and what is termed as “Immoral act”.

Most of these attacks are so harsh and demeaning. Don’t men have failed marriages and relationships? Why is the culture so cruel to women? They are not to be heard, for how long? Despite all odds women are pushing on. Absolutely one day it will be a broken jinx.

Patriarchy theory was displayed here. Sylvia puts it thus: *“A systematic social structure where men hold primary power, dominate roles of political leadership, moral authority and property. It posits that gender inequality is not natural but culturally constructed to maintain male privilege”*

ECONOMIC RESPONSIBILITIES IN POLITICS.

In the Political arena in Nigeria. It is obvious that money not academic qualification, not charisma or good character or credibility is of utmost importance for one to clinch a political seat. Taking into cognizance the importance of money in campaign, Campaigns today are very expensive. Women don’t get sponsored as men are due to gender inequality, invariably very few women can afford the high cost of campaign from party primaries to the main election.

The party tickets are also very high so as to disenable the few aspiring women. There is also a significant disparity in the issuance of loans to women for their campaigns.

“Money is also a tool for direct control and abuse within political and personal sphere”.

“Addressing these financial barrier and pervasive influence of money in politics is considered essential for achieving true gender equality and a more representative democracy”.

SOLUTIONS

From all indications, institutionalizing women’s representation in election officer will put an end to this trauma and ensure a more inclusive governance. The National Youth Leaders of National Political Parties described the bill in the Nigeria National Assembly seeking to institutionalize women’s representation as a “national imperative aimed at correcting long-standing gender imbalance and ensuring that women can express support for the proposed constitutional amendment”.

Amma Bryhm saw it from this perspective;

“... the bill is not just legislation but a rallying point for justice, democracy and nation-building”.

ESTABLISH A COMPREHENSIVE CAMPAIGN MONETARY LAW

Taking for instance what is happening in America

“... the main political parties have launched political action committees (PACs) as partisan networks to fund raise for women candidates. This is the main goal of the Democratic EMILY’s List and the Republican “WISH” List. Those platforms can channel large amounts of money to candidates, which is important in the candidate centered systems where both nomination and campaigning require substantial funding. Through both initiatives, women candidates have benefitted from contribution from individuals and private

sector EMILY’s List (Early Morning is like Yeast) was created in 1985 to support Democratic women candidates running for office by helping them raise funds through donation, bundling, the WISH List was created in 1992 to support Republican Women candidates”.

PARTIES SHOULD SLASH NOMINATION FEES

It’s obvious in Nigeria that no woman has ever been nominated for the post of President in Nigeria since the inception of democracy in 1999. Sarah Jibril the only woman didn’t pass the primaries.

“The APC, the party of President Muhammadu Buhari wants \$125,000 (£97,000) for a nomination form. An opposition PDP Presidential nomination is cheap by comparison. Just \$33,000, Woman on the other hand get a discount half price for the APC or totally free if you want to try your luck with PDP. But neither party has ever nominated a woman since the return of democracy in 1999 and only one woman Sarah Jibril has run in primaries. She gained just one vote in the 2011 contest”.

WE NEED TO WAKE UP IN NIGERIA

Although Buhari, eventually bought the form for \$76,000. Is this not a calculated attempt to prevent qualified Nigerians from accessing the form and also encourage corruption? Alhaji Mumakai Unagha put it thus;

“a deliberate act to deny potential aspirants with genuine intentions for the Country from accessing or collecting the form”.

*A rule must be set for the purchase of forms in every categories from Councillorship to Presidential stage.

*There should be an efficient monitoring team to ensure implantation or else politics in Nigeria will only be for the rich and per chance you get the power you will also recover your money.

“LOOTING” is it not?

Unagha said;

*“The party is indirectly telling Nigerians that when aspirants get to power, they should recoup their money”. By the grace of God, women will persevere and overcome A **Broken Jinx** indeed for they were born to win and rule”.*

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“A women’s place is in the kitchen should not be seen as restrictive but redefined through empowerment and respect. Women today can excel in every field while maintaining pride in their domestic and cultural heritage”.

Ann Oakley quipped:

“Housework is directly opposed to the possibilities of human self-actualization”

Perseverance paves the way. Ann opined, *“Aim at the high mark and you will hit it. No not the first time, not the second time and may be not the third time. But keep on aiming and keep on shooting, for only practice will you perfect”. Don't give up “Great Women of Substance”*

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